

THE VALUE OF LEGAL EDUCATION IN FORMING LEGAL CULTURE

Umarova Shakhlo Baxtiyarovna

TSPI Teacher of Department of " Philosophy and Fundamentals of Spirituality"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10667107>

Abstract. *In this article, the legal culture and the culture of human rights, which are considered to be its components, the construction of a democratic, legal state and its further strengthening in many ways, the question of the role of civil and legal education, including the educational process on human rights focused. In particular, it was said that a high legal culture is the foundation of a democratic society and an expression of the maturity of the legal system.*

Keywords: *legal culture; human rights; democratic state; legal system.*

Just as no field is free from globalization processes, the future development of legal sciences will also largely depend on the impact of globalization processes. A high legal culture is the foundation of a democratic society and an expression of the maturity of the legal system. It is a factor that actively affects various life processes in the society, helps the cohesion of citizens and all social groups, ensures and strengthens the integrity and stability of the society. [3] Respect for the law is one of the main requirements of the legal society and the effective functioning of political and legal systems. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 259 dated on 12.05.2022, which provides for the organization of systematic and comprehensive legal promotion activities based on the conceptual idea of "high legal culture - a guarantee of the country's development", in 2022-2023, the improvement of legal culture in the society It is important that the program of measures has been approved. In 2022-2023, the program of measures to improve legal culture in society provides for the following: [1]

Measures to be implemented on formation of legal education and improvement of legal culture in the family and educational institutions:

providing information about the negative consequences of unrest and violence in the upbringing of children and their prevention;

organization of training courses on human rights, women's rights, children's rights in higher educational institutions and personnel retraining and qualification improvement training centers;

information-propaganda work on the issues of providing benefits and material assistance to the segments of the population in need of social protection, etc.;

Legal culture and the culture of human rights, which are considered to be its component, are considered an integral part of a democratic, legal state, the construction of a democratic legal state in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its further strengthening in many ways, civil and legal education, including human rights. depends on how well the education is organized. Because human rights culture is considered a systematic, gradual and continuous effort to establish human dignity, dignity and human personality, education in the field of human rights, this - education is systematic and purpose-oriented to create a general culture of human rights by instilling knowledge and skills on human rights and forming a point of view, informing about this knowledge, teaching and disseminating it is an effort. [2]

Human rights education focuses on:

- strengthening the attitude of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms;

- all-round development of the human personality, formation of a sense of human dignity and worth in citizens;

- promote mutual understanding, tolerance, equality and friendship between men and women and between all nationalities, indigenous peoples, racial, national, ethnic, religious and linguistic groups;

- to provide opportunities for effective participation in the socio-political and cultural life of society for all people;

- to support the activities of international and national organizations to support peace;

The main goals of education in the field of human rights are as follows: first, to promote a general understanding of the purpose and content of education in the field of human rights; secondly, promoting minimum standards for education in the field of human rights; thirdly, defining the processes and steps necessary for the development, implementation, evaluation and change of national plans for education in the field of human rights; fourth, to draw attention to the human, financial and technical resources needed to develop national approaches to human rights education; fifth, to encourage effective cooperation between national and international organizations dealing with human rights and to help implement international human rights standards at the national level; sixth, to create mechanisms to assess the acceptable goals of human rights education and the levels of their achievement. [4]

Human rights education should enable:

- to respect and understand the fight against discrimination based on race, national or ethnic origin, gender, religion, age, social origin, physical or mental health and other similar characteristics, and diversity based on such characteristics;

- to use non-discriminatory language and non-discriminatory behavior;

- to respect and understand the diversity of opinions;

- to introduce human rights norms in everyday life;

- qualified training of teachers;

- to develop and strengthen national capabilities and knowledge necessary for effective implementation of education in the field of human rights.

Education in the field of human rights encourages the following: first, to help respect and protect all human rights through information and educational activities that cover all members of society; secondly, to promote the interdependence, indivisibility and universality of human rights, including personal, political, economic, social and cultural rights, as well as the right to development; third, integrating women's rights as human rights into all aspects of national development; fourth, to recognize the role of education in the field of human rights as a strategy to prevent the violation of these rights; fifth, to recognize the importance of human rights education in democracy, sustainable development, legal order, environmental protection and peacekeeping; sixth, to encourage the analysis of human rights issues that help to make decisions in accordance with human rights norms; seventh, modern trends of innovative development in science and education in the global, regional, global world for the protection of human rights December 15, 2022. 172 to help acquire knowledge and skills related to the use of national and local documents; eighth, to enable citizens to identify their needs related to human rights and to ensure that these needs are met; ninthly, development of pedagogical sciences that include knowledge, critical analysis and skills for making decisions that allow for the protection of human rights; tenth, to encourage the creation of research and educational materials necessary for the observance of

human rights; eleventh, to help create conditions for education that encourages the voluntary and conscious participation of citizens in the realization of human rights and the full development of the human personality. [5]

One of the important directions of the political reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is to democratize and liberalize all spheres of the political life of our country, the construction of the state and society, to increase the political activity of the population, and to form a political culture based on national and universal values. In this process, it is necessary to make democracy, freedom of thought and conscience, pluralism and human rights, and living in accordance with the principles of humanism the main criteria of society's life, but also at the international level began to be given great importance.

In short, the processes of globalization in the world have an impact on national democratic development, socio-demographic situation, immigration, economic, political and cultural life in Uzbekistan. The fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan strives to take a place in the world community and develop through integration makes globalization a common reality in our national life. Globalization is pushing legal culture out of the narrow national shell. Now citizens should also know international legal norms and have a minimum knowledge about them. Because, in order to build the legal democratic state that we aim for, the population must be sufficiently legally literate and legally cultured. Because the importance of human rights as a universal human value began to be paid attention to.

REFERENCES

1. Prezidentning 2019 yil 9 yanvardagi PF-5618-son Farmoni.
2. https://www.norma.uz/qonunchilikda_yangi/jamiyatda_huquqiy_madaniyatni_yuksaltirish_qanday_rejalashtirilmogda.
3. Kadirova, X. B. (2023). YOSHLARNI MILLIY QADRIYATLAR RUHIDA TARBIYALASHDA OILALA VA MAHALLALARNING RO'LI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(10), 549-554.
4. Buvabayevna, K. X. (2023). YOSHLARNING HUQUQIY MADANIYATNI SHAKILLANTIRISHDA IJTIMOIIY-MA'NAVIY MUXITNING TA'SIRI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 879-884.
5. Odilqoriyev H.T., O'zbekiston davlati va jamiyati innovasion rivojlanishining huquqiy jihatlari/O'quv qo'llanma. – T.: INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH NASHRIYOT MATBAA UYI, 2019. – 362 b.
6. Кадырова, Я. Б. YOSHLARDA FUKAROLIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH ORQALI VATANPARVARLIK VA BAYNALMINALLIK TUYG'ULARINI, RIVOJLANTIRISH/JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH. 2023/2/25.B-197-202
7. Kadirova, Y. B. (2023). TA'LIM JARAYONIDA O'QITISHNING INTEGRATIV TEXNOLOGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQUV VA AMALIYOTIDA QO'LLASH. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(10), 541-548.
8. [Y Kadirova, K Kadirova SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF PEDAGOGUE IN SOCIO-POLITICAL LIFE OF SOCIETY](#)//Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B3. – Pp. 417-421

9. Kadirova Yakitjan Buvabaevna, Kadirova Khalima Buvabaevna. [METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL IMMUNITY OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A SUBJECT-ETHICAL APPROACH](#). Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. 2022/12/23. Pp.6480-6487. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S09.771>
10. Kadirova, Y. B. (2024). CHANGES IN THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS SOUTHERN REGIONS DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT*, 3(1), 136-143.
11. Buvabaevna, K. H. (2023). VALUE OF DEVELOPING MEDIA LITERACY, MEDIA EDUCATION, INFORMATION CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 2(9), 23-27
12. Кади́рова, Х. Б. (2015). ОСОБЕННОСТИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СЕМЕЙ. *ФЭн-наука*, (10), 11-12.
13. Kadirova Y. LOVING THE COUNTRY IS FAITHFUL //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. B4. – С. 420-423.
14. Kadirova Y. B. The Advantages of Improving Students' Civic Literacy in Building a Democratic State Governed by the Rule of Law //International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 5. – С. 469-473.
15. Buvabaevna K. Y. Issues of Civil Literacy Development in the Education System //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 5477-5489.